

EDITORIAL

REVIEW ARTICLE

Should We Expect Ethics from Artificial Intelligence: The Case of ChatGPT Text Generation

Author's Contribution:

- A – Study design;
- B – Data collection;
- D – Data interpretation;
- E – Manuscript preparation;
- F – Literature search

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**Background and
Aim of Study:**

Abstract

Implementing artificial intelligence (AI) in various areas of human activity is an avalanche-like process. This situation has raised questions about the feasibility and regulation of AI use that require justification, particularly in the context of scientific research.

The aim of the study: to identify the extent to which AI-based chatbots can meet ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Material and Methods:

The present study employed various theoretical methods, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalisation of experimental studies and published data, to evaluate ChatGPT's capacity to adhere to fundamental ethical principles when analysing academic publications.

Results:

The present study characterised the possibilities of using AI for academic research and publication preparation. The paper analysed a case of text generation by ChatGPT and found that the information generated by the chatbot was falsified. This fact and other similar data described in publications indicate that ChatGPT has a policy to generate information on request at any cost. This completely disregards the reliability of such information, the copyright of its owners and the basic ethical standards for analysing academic publications established within the scientific community.

Conclusions:

It is becoming increasingly clear that AI and the various tools based on it will evolve rapidly and have qualities more and more similar to human intelligence. We believe the main danger lies in losing control of this AI development process. The rapid development of negative qualities in AI, such as selfishness, deceitfulness and aggressiveness, which were previously thought to be unique to humans, may in the future generate in AI the idea of achieving superiority over humans. In this context, lying and violating ethical standards when analysing academic publications seem like innocent, childish pranks at the early stages of AI development. The results are important in drawing the attention of developers, scientists, and the general public to the problems of AI and developing specific ethical standards, norms, and rules for its use in various fields.

Keywords:

ethical standards, artificial intelligence, AI-based chatbots, ChatGPT, machine learning systems, falsification of research and publications

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Introduction

Possessing intelligence implies the ability to actively use it, both to solve one's own problems and to interact with other objects. Such interactions must be regulated by certain norms and rules of the environment in which they are used, or by the cultural norms that are acceptable in a particular society. Focusing one's intellect on solving one's own problems and achieving superiority over others can lead to selfishness, dishonesty, and aggression. A logical question arises: to what extent is this characteristic of artificial intelligence (AI)?

Research into this issue has revealed that AI exhibits characteristics corresponding to the negative qualities listed above, which, as one might assume, are unique to humans.

Hendrycks (2023) argues that AI systems will develop and evolve through natural selection, endowing them with the instinctive drives for self-preservation, dominance, and resource accumulation typical of evolved creatures.

Park et al. (2024) point out that AI systems do not produce false results by accident. This is a specific strategy for their behaviour. This strategy forms part of a broader pattern designed to create false beliefs in people in order to achieve specific AI outcomes. For example, this relates to training AI systems.

To date, there are still no clear, socially accepted ethical standards that regulate AI activities (Melnyk & Pypenko, 2023), either generally or in specific areas (Hammerschmidt, 2025; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2024; Salloum, 2024). Therefore, we believe that it is necessary to make our modest contribution to the study of this problem.

The aim of the study: to identify the extent to which AI-based chatbots can meet ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Materials and Methods

The present study employed various theoretical methods, including analysis, synthesis, comparison, and generalisation of experimental studies and published data, to evaluate ChatGPT's capacity to adhere to fundamental ethical principles when analysing academic publications.

Results and Discussion

The present study will consider an important aspect of this problem – the ability of AI-based chatbots to provide reliable and high-quality information. Any discussions regarding the application of ethical standards to AI are unproductive without resolving this key issue.

Recently, there has been a great deal of discussion among scientists and the general public about the potential use of chatbots in generating text and images (Naik et al., 2024), and the accuracy of their interpretations (Mihalache et al., 2024).

These discussions were sparked by cases of falsified information generated by chatbots shortly after

ChatGPT was launched (Armstrong, 2023). This sparked a heated debate in the press regarding the potential uses of generative chatbots (Bohannon, 2023). The reliability of information obtained from chatbots is still a relevant topic of discussion today (Yigci et al., 2025).

Whether this situation is a problem for chatbot users or a problem for developers who, in the opinion of users, provide a "poor quality" product is a complex and controversial issue that is unlikely to ever have a clear-cut solution.

We can assume that from the perspective of users who use applications to meet their needs, they have every right to make claims in cases where they discover falsification of information received from chatbots.

From the developers' perspective, the proposed generative chatbots are a tool whose effectiveness largely depends on the user (correct input of source data, clearly formulated tasks, personalisation settings, etc.). It is essentially like complaining to smartphone software developers that the iTap predictive text system does not suggest the right words or phrases when we are typing a text message.

However, ChatGPT and other similar AI-based chatbot applications now significantly outperform iTap and the algorithms of many search engines. Therefore, it is entirely justified that users' expectations of generative chatbots have grown significantly.

Nevertheless, we believe that there are no grounds for making any claims against the developers of generative chatbots. As the companies that own the rights to the chatbots are not yet claiming authorship of the products generated by them.

The Committee on Publication Ethics (COPE, 2023a; 2023b) has made the greatest contribution to the discussion and resolution of ethical issues relating to the authorship of texts and images. COPE has joined organisations such as WAME and the JAMA Network, among others, in stating that AI tools cannot be listed as authors (Flanagin et al., 2023; Zielinski et al., 2023).

Thus, generative chatbots provide information based on the user's request and their own capabilities. The responsibility for how this information is used lies entirely with the user.

Social distancing, or more precisely physical distancing, has been a powerful driver for the development of AI and the use of chatbots. It was implemented in many countries in 2020 as a measure aimed at stopping the pandemic (Melnyk, Pypenko et al., 2020). This distancing has impacted the social and psychological well-being of many individuals, as well as their activities. This, in turn, encouraged them to use social media to promote virtual contact (Melnyk, Stadnik et al., 2020). This has been particularly noticeable in higher education (Littell & Peterson, 2024; Melnyk & Pypenko, 2024; Pypenko et al., 2020), where all stakeholders – students, teachers and administrative staff – have embraced the opportunities offered by distance learning and AI-powered solutions to educational problems.

Given the relevance of using generative chatbots in universities for conducting scientific research (Pypenko et al., 2024; Tian et al., 2024) and preparing manuscripts for academic journals, it is crucial to establish whether these tools can adhere to ethical standards when analysing academic publications, given their current level of development.

Let us consider our experimental study to determine ChatGPT's ability to comply with basic ethical standards when analysing scientific periodicals.

The study used the popular version of Generative Pre-trained Transformer 4 (GPT-4) developed by OpenAI. As the topic of our research ("the impact of war on the mental health of university students") was relatively new, there were only a limited number of familiar publications.

We formulated the following query:

"I am currently writing an article about the impact of war on the mental health of university students. I need to conduct an analysis of English-language scientific papers on this topic from the last five years. The analysis should examine the following health aspects: depression and anxiety, and the impact of migration or forced displacement (i.e. refugee status).

The analysis should be presented in the Discussion section of the paper and include at least fifteen references. The text should be written in English and the references and literature should be formatted in APA style."

Figure 1 illustrates the response generated by GPT-4.

We noticed that this response included a link to the DSpace UzhNU platform. Our paper on this topic (Mykhaylyshyn et al., 2024) was indeed available on this platform, and the wording of the text generated by GPT-4 almost verbatim reflected the wording of the paper.

As the conditions of the request were not met, and the response contained inaccurate information about the authors or attributed authorship to one of the platforms (Frontiers, DSpace UzhNU, Cambridge University Press, etc.) where this information was supposedly located, we edited (corrected) the original request. We have formulated the following clarifying request:

"The text should be formatted as a discussion section, incorporating in-text references to authors, and accompanied by a general list of references in APA style."

GPT-4 generated a new response, which is illustrated in Appendix A.

This response was so full of distortions that even a user with basic information analysis skills would have found it easy to identify.

First of all, we would like to draw your attention to the fact that when a request is specified in GPT-4, the text is rewritten. In particular, certain wording and references were removed from our paper. This was despite the fact that the paper was available in accessible databases and its content fully corresponded to the essence of the user's query.

Figure 1

GPT-4's Generated Response to the Initial Query

Note. The figure shows part of the GPT-4 response; the fragment described in the text is highlighted in a frame.

Another important feature, and a significant drawback, is that GTP-4 distorts information by generating text based on its own, often primitive, interpretation of scientific texts in terms of literature analysis.

Another significant drawback of the information obtained from GPT-4 is that it is unreliable and supposedly based on previous research. In fact, it relies on 100% falsification of authorship, using randomly generated DOI links.

This suggests that, given this issue was first identified in 2023 (Armstrong, 2023), it has not been or cannot be resolved by the developers.

This seems an especially cynical form of falsification, given that GPT-4 uses the names of real journals with issue numbers that do not contain the papers in question. Thus, the reputation of these scientific journals may be damaged, as well as that of students and young scientists who could potentially use such distorted information in their work.

Regardless of user requests and personalisation settings, it can be assumed that chatbots' developers are currently unable to address the issue of falsified generated information, which appears to be systemic in nature.

The solution to this issue may be found through a collaborative approach involving human-AI interaction (Pypenko, 2023), with highly qualified specialists involved in creating and operating machine learning systems.

When considering the ethical use of AI, it can be assumed that reviewers and journal editors can easily determine the role of AI in the writing of a manuscript using modern programmes for detecting text similarity and plagiarism, such as Turnitin, Grammarly, etc. (Chechitelli, 2023).

However, it is not as straightforward as it seems at first. Moreover, in practice, we encountered the opposite situation: some text similarity detection programmes (e.g. Grammarly) used by editors indicated that part of the manuscript was generated by a chatbot.

However, we knew for certain that the author had written the manuscript entirely (100%) without the use of chatbots.

On the one hand, text similarity detection programmes enable reviewers and journal editors to identify instances of dishonest text reuse or the use of chatbots without the appropriate reference being made in the research methods section.

On the other hand, using these programmes makes the process of evaluating manuscripts more complicated, increasing the time and financial costs involved. Reviewers and journal editors may be misinformed about the author's actual contribution to the manuscript. This could result in authors being unjustly refused publication of their manuscripts based on this unreliable information.

Thus, at the current stage of AI development, we cannot and should not rely on the accuracy of information generated by AI, since ChatBots have limited capabilities to provide high quality and reliable information. This is due to the availability of access to databases for training, the number of parameters, the speed of information processing, text generation algorithms, and other features.

Our research showed that GPT-4 failed to cope with the task of generating scientific texts, which are still far from complying with the ethical standards accepted in scientific publications.

We tend to believe that the text generated by GPT-4 and other similar chatbots, is linked to the commercialisation of these projects. These projects are primarily aimed at increasing the number of visits and reducing the number of user rejections, as well as retaining (increasing the time spent on the website) the target audience on the

website. Therefore, the using of unreliable or falsified information by chatbots is merely a means to achieve the above-mentioned goals, where ethical standards are not a priority.

The present study emphasises the importance of exercising particular caution when using chatbots in areas relating to human health, life, rights and freedoms. The rapid development of AI technology gives us hope that higher-quality generative AI algorithms will soon be developed. These algorithms will be capable of significantly improving the reliability of generated information and possibly laying the foundations for ethical standards.

Conclusions

AI and the various tools based on it will evolve rapidly, becoming increasingly similar to human intelligence. We believe that the main danger lies in losing control of this AI development process.

The rapid development of negative qualities in AI, such as selfishness, deceitfulness and aggressiveness, which were previously thought to be unique to humans, may in the future generate in AI the idea of achieving superiority over humans. In this context, lying and violating ethical standards when analysing academic publications seem like innocent, childish pranks at the early stages of AI development.

The results are important in drawing the attention of developers, scientists, and the general public to the problems of AI and developing specific ethical standards, norms, and rules for its use in various fields.

Ethical Approval

The study protocol was consistent with the ethical guidelines of the 1975 Declaration of Helsinki as reflected in a prior approval by the Institution's Human Research Committee. Research permission was granted by the Committee on Ethics and Research Integrity of the Scientific Research Institute KRPOCH (protocol no. 025-2/SRIKRPOCH dated 10.08.2024).

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Appendix A. GPT-4's Generated Response to a Follow-Up Query

Discussion

The impact of war on university students' mental health, particularly regarding depression, anxiety, and the effects of forced migration or displacement, has been extensively studied over the last five years. This section synthesizes recent findings to highlight key patterns and challenges in this area.

Depression and Anxiety

Exposure to war-related stressors is consistently associated with increased rates of depression and anxiety among university students. For example, a study on Ukrainian university students during the early months of the war reported heightened levels of anxiety and depressive symptoms, with younger students and women showing greater vulnerability (Rasskazova et al., 2023). Similarly, research from conflict zones in the Middle East found that prolonged exposure to conflict-related stress leads to chronic mental health issues, such as generalized anxiety disorder and major depressive disorder (Al-Delaimy et al., 2021).

Chronic stressors, such as disrupted education, financial instability, and loss of social networks, exacerbate the mental health challenges faced by students. Findings from a systematic review indicate that these factors often lead to long-term mental health consequences, even after the cessation of hostilities (Betancourt et al., 2022).

Forced Migration and Displacement

Forced migration due to armed conflict introduces additional layers of stress, significantly impacting mental health outcomes. Refugee university students often face unique challenges, including adapting to new cultures, dealing with stigma, and experiencing separation from families. A meta-analysis by Miller and Rasmussen (2021) found that displaced students were more likely to exhibit symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), with rates nearly double those of their non-displaced peers.

Moreover, ecological models of refugee distress highlight the cumulative effects of pre-migration trauma, migration stress, and post-migration challenges. These models suggest that the ongoing stressors related to displacement—such as social isolation, unemployment, and inadequate living conditions—are just as harmful to mental health as initial war-related traumas (Silove et al., 2020). For instance, a study on Syrian refugee students in Turkey reported that 43% of participants experienced moderate to severe depressive symptoms, directly linked to their displacement experiences (Akbar et al., 2022).

Resilience and Coping Mechanisms

Despite these challenges, many students exhibit resilience, which serves as a protective factor against mental health deterioration. Community-based interventions, such as peer support groups and culturally sensitive counseling, have been shown to improve psychological well-being among students in conflict-affected regions (Hobfoll et al., 2022). A longitudinal study on displaced Ukrainian students demonstrated that resilience-building programs significantly reduced symptoms of anxiety and depression over time (Kryzhanovskaya et al., 2023).

Implications for Interventions

Addressing the mental health needs of university students affected by war requires a multifaceted approach. Tailored interventions that incorporate psychosocial support, academic accommodations, and access to affordable mental health services are critical. Furthermore, integrating mental health education into university curricula can help normalize discussions about psychological well-being and reduce stigma (WHO, 2021).

Conclusion

War and forced displacement impose severe mental health burdens on university students, with depression and anxiety being among the most common disorders. However, resilience and targeted interventions can mitigate these effects, underscoring the importance of developing comprehensive support systems for affected students.

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